

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL 2: List of microstructural characters according to the corresponding aligned matrix

ITS

SSR motif and base pair positions:
CTC 75-77

GAP base pair position(s):

67-68
69-71
71
79-80
110-111
121-122
125
128-130
169
181
187
203-204
203
212
556
566-567
586-598
607
609-615
624-627

ndhF-rpl32

SSR motif and base pair positions:
AATATT 126-131
AAGATAAAC? with mutation 257-266
CATTA 307-312
CACTTTATAAA 347-357
AG 600-601

GAP base pair position(s):

276
437-445
449-662